

1 Enzyme-assisted supercritical carbon dioxide extraction of black pepper oleoresin for
2 enhanced yield of piperine-rich extract

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20 **Black pepper (*Piper nigrum* L.), the ‘King of Spices’ is the most popular spice**
21 **globally and its active ingredient, piperine, is reportedly known for its therapeutic**
22 **potency. In this work, enzyme assisted supercritical carbon dioxide (SC-CO₂) extraction**
23 **of black pepper oleoresin was investigated using α -amylase (from *Bacillus licheniformis*)**
24 **for enhanced yield of piperine-rich extract possessing good combination of**
25 **phytochemical properties. Optimization of the extraction parameters (without enzyme),**
26 **mainly temperature and pressure, was conducted in both batch and continuous modes**
27 **and the optimized conditions that provided the maximum yield of piperine was in the**
28 **batch mode, with a sample size of 20 g of black pepper powder (particle diameter $0.42 \pm$**
29 **0.02 mm) at 60°C and 300 bar at 2 L/min of CO₂ flow. Studies on activity of α -amylase**
30 **were conducted under these optimized conditions in both batch and continuous modes,**
31 **with varying amounts of lyophilized enzyme (2 mg, 5 mg and 10 mg) and time of**
32 **exposure of the enzyme to SC-CO₂ (2.25 h and 4.25 h). The specific activity of the**
33 **enzyme increased by 2.13 times when treated in the continuous mode than in the batch**
34 **mode (1.25 times increase). The structural changes of the treated enzymes were studied**
35 **by ¹H NMR analyses. In case of α -amylase assisted extractions of black pepper, both**
36 **batch and continuous modes significantly increased the yields and phytochemical**
37 **properties of piperine-rich extracts; with higher increase in batch mode than in**
38 **continuous.**

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40 **[Key words: Black pepper; Piperine; Supercritical carbon dioxide extraction; Batch and**
41 **continuous mode; α -amylase; Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR)]**

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43 Black pepper, the ‘King of Spices’ is the most popular globally used spice, used
44 extensively in Ayurvedic medicines, in food products and in cosmetics. It is the dried, fully
45 mature, unripe berry of *Piper nigrum* L., a perennial climber belonging to the family
46 Piperaceae, native to the evergreen forests in the Western Ghats of South India (1).
47 According to the data reported by Indian Agribusiness Systems Private Limited, 4574 tons of
48 black pepper worth USD 9,500.00 per ton has been exported from India in February 2014
49 (Spices-Monthly-Research-Report, 2014) (2). The characteristic aroma and flavor of black
50 pepper is contributed mostly by its oleoresin, principally piperine, which is priced at USD
51 190.30 per kg (Export Analysis and trends of piperine, 2014) (3). India alone exported
52 piperine worth USD 24,560.00 and oleoresin worth USD 2,239,330.00 in February 2014
53 (Export Analysis and trends of black pepper oleoresin) (3,4). Black pepper possesses several
54 physiological effects, such as strong antioxidative effects; besides stimulating digestive
55 capacity, reducing gastrointestinal food transit time and enhancing bioavailability of several
56 therapeutic drugs and phytochemicals (5).

57 Conventional extraction of essential oil from black pepper is carried out by
58 hydrodistillation using Clevenger apparatus. Although water is the greenest solvent, it cannot
59 solubilize piperine, the active principle of black pepper. Extraction of piperine is therefore
60 reportedly carried out using solvent extraction in Soxhlet assembly and in standard shake
61 flasks. These solvent extraction techniques are relatively inexpensive; however, the
62 drawbacks of these methods include energy and time consumption, thermal degradation,
63 hydrolysis of desirable constituents, presence of artifacts and traces of solvents in the extracts
64 (6). Owing to these, there are stringent global regulations on usage of these solvents. These
65 limitations necessitate exploration of alternative green extraction techniques, such as
66 supercritical fluid extraction (SFE), well suited for extraction of solvent-free, bioactive-rich
67 natural extracts for food and therapeutic applications (7).

68 SFE uses fluids above their critical points with liquid like densities leading to high
69 loadings of solutes. This coupled with their pressure-dependent solvating abilities, renders
70 them excellent solvents for separations and reactions. Their low viscosities and high
71 molecular diffusivities like gases, combined with low surface tension, makes them very
72 amenable for mass transfer, allowing better penetration into sample matrices and faster,
73 selective extraction of desired compounds. The most commonly used fluid for SFE is carbon
74 dioxide ($T_c = 31.1^\circ\text{C}$, $P_c = 73.8$ bar) which is clean, non-inflammable, non-toxic, eco-friendly
75 and generally regarded as safe (GRAS) solvent (7).

76 There have been studies on fixed bed extraction of essential oil and oleoresin fractions of
77 black pepper using supercritical carbon dioxide (SC-CO₂) extraction (8-12). Ferreira et al.
78 (11) have reported 2.1% yield of essential oil (at 50°C and 300 bar) from the same; while
79 Tipsrisukond et al. (12) have extracted black pepper oleoresin by SC-CO₂ at 45°C and 320
80 bar and reported 39.4% relative extraction rate of piperine. Sovová et al. (13) have also
81 worked on black pepper oleoresin at 280 bar and 24 to 60°C and reported extraction of 30 to
82 60% of total piperine in the oleoresin fraction.

83 The best Indian black pepper known worldwide for its excellent aroma, flavor and
84 pungency is the Malabar variety (14). In our study, we have investigated this variety for SC-
85 CO₂ extraction of its oleoresin fraction (principally piperine). However, the yield of piperine
86 (1.2 ± 0.1 mg/g dry black pepper which corresponds to 22.7% of total piperine in black
87 pepper) obtained in our study was lower than that reported in literature. Proximate analysis of
88 the raw material revealed that the main constituent of black pepper is carbohydrate ($58.4 \pm$
89 0.1%). Starch ($30.4 \pm 0.1\%$) was the predominant carbohydrate in our sample, in agreement
90 with Pruthi (15) who reported starch content of black pepper to be 34.8%. We opine that
91 starch being one of the major constituents of black pepper coat, could possibly impede

92 extraction of piperine by thwarting it's accessibility to solvents and would result in poor yield
93 of the same. Therefore, for improved release of oleoresin and piperine from black pepper,
94 hydrolysis of this starch would be necessary. Use of starch degrading enzymes, such as α -
95 amylase (E.C. 3.2.1.1.) for pretreatment of the pepper matrix prior to extraction would render
96 extraction easy and improve yield of extracts. This has been affirmed by Lee et al. (16), who
97 reported hydrolysis of corn starch by α -amylase and glucoamylase for improved recovery
98 (40%) of reducing sugars.

99 There are reports on use of other enzymes under SC-CO₂ extraction conditions. Chandran
100 et al. (17) conducted enzyme-assisted hydrodistillation of black pepper and cardamom. They
101 have obtained improved yield of essential oil (0.9 to 1.8% increase) and its major components
102 (β -caryophyllene markedly increased from 15.0 to 25.6%) by pre-treatment of the sample
103 matrix with a mixture of cellulase, β -glucanase, pectinase and xylanase. SC-CO₂ conditions
104 have also been employed in enzyme-assisted synthesis of dipalmitin from palmitic acid and
105 glycerol by immobilized lipase (18); for enzymatic ring-opening polymerization of Poly (ϵ -
106 caprolactone) (PCL) using lipase B (19) and in acylation of fibrous cellulose by immobilized
107 lipase, immobilized esterase and immobilized cutinase (20), to state a few. All these authors
108 have reported on batch mode of enzyme-assisted SC-CO₂ extractions. Senyay-Oncel and
109 Yesil-Celiktas (21) reported an increase in activity and stability of fungal α -amylase
110 employing dynamic (continuous) mode of SC-CO₂ conditions.

111 To the best of our knowledge, there is no report on use of α -amylase for SC-CO₂ extraction
112 of black pepper oleoresin. *Aspergillus oryzae*, *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens*, *Bacillus subtilis*
113 and *Bacillus licheniformis* are known to be commercial sources of α -amylase. Apar and
114 Özbek (22) have reported that α -amylase obtained from *Bacillus licheniformis* showed
115 maximum degrees of hydrolysis for corn, rice and wheat starch (40.4%, 48.1% and 58.1%

116 respectively) compared to that obtained by *Bacillus species* (5.5%, 19.1% and 29.1%,
117 respectively) and *Aspergillus oryzae* (0%, 0% and 17.5% respectively). Hence, *Bacillus*
118 *licheniformis* has been selected as the source of α -amylase in our studies.

119 In the present investigation, a combination of α -amylase and SC-CO₂ extraction was
120 employed for single step hydrolysis of black pepper starch and extraction of the oleoresin
121 fraction from the hydrolyzed matrix. The novelty of our study is that it reports for the first
122 time on enzyme-assisted extraction of oleoresin from black pepper by SC-CO₂. Both batch
123 and continuous modes of extraction (discussed later) were employed to enhance the yield of
124 piperine-rich extract possessing good combination of phytochemical properties, such as total
125 phenolic content, reducing power, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities. This extract
126 would have promising usage as food and therapeutic supplements.

127 MATERIALS AND METHODS

128 **Materials** Malabar Garbled black pepper was procured from Spices Board, Cochin,
129 India. Standard piperine (97% pure), α -amylase from *Bacillus licheniformis* (lyophilized
130 powder, 500-1500 units/mg protein, 93-100% SDS PAGE), soluble potato starch, 1,1-
131 diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), sodium nitroprusside (Na₂[Fe(CN)₅NO].2H₂O), Griess
132 reagent and gallic acid were procured from M/s Sigma, India; Na₂SO₄, NaH₂PO₄, NaCl,
133 NaOH, Na₂CO₃, CuSO₄.5H₂O, K₃Fe(CN)₆, FeCl₃, TCA, Folin-Ciocalteu's phenol reagent
134 (FCR), potassium sodium tartrate tetrahydrate, methanol, ethanol and *n*-hexane were
135 procured from M/s E-Merck, India. 3,5-Dinitrosalicylic acid (DNSA) was purchased from
136 M/s Himedia, India. All chemicals were of AR grade. 3 mL SPE cartridge and cartridge
137 holder were purchased from M/s Applied Separations (Allentown, USA).

138 **Characterization of black pepper powder** Black pepper berries were ground using an
139 electric mixer grinder (HL 1618, M/s Philips, India) and particle diameters were determined

140 using the sieve analysis method by screening the black pepper powder through a set of
141 standard sieves in a sieve shaker in accordance to the method reported by Bhattacharjee et al.
142 (23). Samples with mean particle diameter ($d_p = 0.42 \pm 0.02$ mm) were subjected to
143 proximate analyses by standard methods in which moisture (Dean and Stark method, AOAC
144 official method 986.21) (24); protein (Kjeldahl method, AOAC official method 984.13) (25);
145 fat (AOAC official method 920.39A) (26); crude fibre (AOAC official method 978.10) (27);
146 ash (AOAC official method 942.05) (28); carbohydrates (by difference) and total starch
147 (Direct acid hydrolysis, ASTA method 8.0) (29) were determined.

148 **Extraction of essential oil and oleoresin from black pepper by conventional methods**

149 100 g of ground black pepper ($d_p = 0.42 \pm 0.02$ mm) was subjected to hydrodistillation for 8 h
150 using Clevenger apparatus, in accordance with Politeo et al. (30), who conducted the same
151 for 3 h. The essential oil obtained was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate for gravimetric
152 estimation.

153 Solvent extractions of black pepper oleoresin were carried out in Soxhlet apparatus, reflux
154 heating assembly and shake flasks. For Soxhlet extraction, 5 g ground black pepper was
155 extracted with *n*-hexane for 8 h (AOAC method 920.39) (26). In the reflux method, 10 g
156 ground black pepper and 50 mL ethanol were set for reflux heating for 1 h at $50 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ in
157 accordance to the method reported by Musenga et al. (31), who conducted the same with 2.5
158 g pepper powder in 15 mL methanol. The solvent was filtered by Whatman No.1 filter paper
159 and the residue was re-extracted by the same process. We also conducted extraction using
160 shake flask method in which 10 g ground black pepper was subjected to extraction using 50
161 mL ethanol at 60°C in an incubator shaker (110 rpm) (M/s INCON, India, Model IS 02) for 1
162 h and for 3 h in separate batches. The extracts collected in all the three methods of solvent
163 extraction were concentrated by rotary vacuum evaporator (M/s Eyela Corp., Japan) at 40-

164 45°C and 0.05 bar Hg and stored in amber colored screw capped vials in an inert atmosphere
165 of nitrogen at 4°C in dark, until further analyses.

166 **SC-CO₂ extraction of black pepper oleoresin** For SC-CO₂ extraction, a SPE-ED SFE 2
167 model of M/s Applied Separations, Allentown, USA, was employed. The system comprises
168 of a modifier pump (Speed MAX P/N 7025) fitted with refrigerated cooling bath to chill the
169 pump head at -2°C. This maintains the required pressure inside the SFE vessel (SS 316) by
170 pumping CO₂ into the extraction vessel placed in the oven module. An air compressor
171 provides compressed air to build pressure inside the extraction vessel. In the static time of
172 extraction, CO₂ was passed through the extraction vessel keeping the outlet valve closed.
173 During the dynamic time, the outlet valve was kept open and at reduced temperature and
174 pressure conditions, the extract precipitated in the collection vial and CO₂ in gaseous form
175 vented out into the atmosphere. At the collection end, a micrometering valve was used to
176 regulate the flow rate of CO₂ in the collection module and the flow rate of gaseous CO₂ was
177 measured by a bubble flow meter under ambient conditions (1 bar and 25±2°C).

178 20 g of ground black pepper ($d_p = 0.42 \pm 0.02$ mm) was charged into a 50 mL extraction
179 vessel. Based on the preliminary trial runs, optimization of extraction temperature and
180 pressure for maximum yield of bioactive compounds was carried out using a three-level
181 factorial design. Extraction temperatures (40°C, 50°C and 60°C) and extraction pressures
182 (200 bar, 300 bar and 500 bar) were investigated. The total extraction time (static time +
183 dynamic time) was kept constant at 45 min (static time of 30 min and dynamic time of 15
184 min, beyond which there was no extract obtained in the collection vial). It was found that the
185 flow rate of CO₂ above 2 L/min resulted in sputtering of the extract in the wall of the
186 collection vial and carryover and entrainment of the same in the outlet tubing leading to loss
187 in extract yields. Therefore, the flow rate of CO₂ was maintained constant at 2 L/min for all
188 experiments. Extracts were collected in screw capped glass vials in an ice bath and stored in

189 amber colored screw capped vials after dissolving in methanol. Based on the yield and
190 phytochemical properties of the extracts, SC-CO₂ conditions were optimized at 60°C and 300
191 bar and these conditions were maintained in the latter experiments.

192 **SC-CO₂ treatment of α -amylase** SC-CO₂ treatment of α -amylase was conducted in our
193 study to investigate whether the specific activity of the treated enzyme showed improved
194 activity. The lyophilized enzyme was subjected to SC-CO₂ conditions inside a SPE cartridge
195 (with cartridge-holder) and the specific activity of the SC-CO₂ treated enzyme was assayed.

196 The enzyme treatment was conducted in both batch and continuous modes. In the batch
197 mode, both static and dynamic time of extraction were employed while continuous mode as
198 conducted in dynamic time of extraction alone. In batch mode, CO₂ was allowed to flush
199 through the extraction vessel for a certain period of static (equilibration) time during which
200 the outlet valve was kept closed. After sufficient static time, the extract was recovered
201 through the outlet and micrometering valves (discussed above). The inlet valve remained
202 open throughout the batch mode while the outlet valve was opened only during the dynamic
203 time of extraction. In continuous mode, the CO₂ entering through the inlet valve into the
204 sample matrix (enzyme bed inside the cartridge) in the vessel was discharged through the
205 outlet valve along with the extract at constant flow rate of 1 L/min. Both the inlet and outlet
206 valves were kept open in the continuous mode which maintained the pressure inside the
207 extraction vessel through the pump module and air compressor unit.

208 The enzyme was treated in batch mode for 1.25 h, 2.25 h and 4.25 h. Results showed that
209 time of contact below 2.25 h did not improve enzyme activity (data not shown) and
210 maximum increase of specific activity was achieved at 2.25 h. Therefore enzymatic treatment
211 under continuous mode was conducted for 2.25 h.

212 **Enzyme-assisted SC-CO₂ extraction of black pepper oleoresin** For enzyme-assisted
213 extraction of black pepper oleoresin by SC-CO₂, the powdered pepper sample was mixed

214 with the lyophilized enzyme in optimized ratio (enzyme : black pepper powder = 1 : 5000)
215 and subjected to batch and continuous modes of extraction. Similar to above, in the batch
216 mode, under supercritical conditions of CO₂ at 60°C and 300 bar, static time was provided to
217 the sample matrix after which collection of the extract (dynamic time) at a fixed flow rate of
218 CO₂ commenced; whereas, in continuous mode, there was a constant flow of CO₂ through the
219 sample matrix at 1 L/min for the entire duration of extraction (without prior equilibration
220 time). Therefore, in batch mode, the enzyme had sufficient incubation time to act on the
221 starch; while in the continuous mode, there was no static time of contact of the starch with the
222 enzyme. These studies with the sample matrix were conducted using both SPE cartridge and
223 SFE vessel.

224 **α-amylase in batch mode in SC-CO₂ conditions** Lyophilized α-amylase powder was
225 loaded to SPE cartridge in different batch sizes (2 mg, 5 mg and 10 mg enzyme) and charged
226 to the SC-CO₂ extraction unit. The top of the cartridge was sealed with two polypropylene
227 frits and the void inside was filled with glass beads (Fig. 1). The loaded SPE cartridge was
228 packed into the SFE vessel with the help of a teflon cartridge-holder and experiments were
229 performed at 60°C and 300 bar by varying the time of exposure of the enzyme (discussed
230 earlier). After SC-CO₂ treatment, CO₂ was released from the vessel and the treated enzymes
231 were immediately recovered in 20 mM sodium phosphate buffer with 6.7 mM NaCl of pH
232 6.9.

233 **Determination of specific activity of enzyme** Enzyme activity was determined using
234 DNSA method (32) by estimation of mg of maltose produced during hydrolysis of 1%
235 soluble potato starch in 20 mM sodium phosphate buffer with 6.7 mM NaCl at pH 6.9. One
236 unit of enzyme liberates 1 mg of maltose from starch per 3 min at pH 6.9 at 20°C. Amount of
237 maltose produced was estimated from its standard curve by measuring the absorbance at 540
238 nm in a UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (U-2000, M/s Hitachi Corp., Kyoto, Japan). To

239 determine specific activity of the enzyme, protein content of the enzyme samples was
240 estimated by Folin-Lowry method (33).

241 **Enzyme-assisted SC-CO₂ extraction of black pepper oleoresin in batch mode** To
242 increase the yield of extraction by hydrolysis of starch of black pepper, 2 g of black pepper
243 was loaded to a SPE cartridge along with 0.4 mg α -amylase and subjected to SC-CO₂
244 extraction at 60°C and 300 bar for 2.25 h (2 h static and 15 min dynamic time). The
245 extraction was carried out with 2 L/min flow rate of CO₂. Enzyme showed maximum activity
246 at 2.25 h of treatment; therefore 4.25 h was no longer investigated for enzyme-assisted
247 extraction of black pepper oleoresin.

248 The optimization of SC-CO₂ conditions for extraction of black pepper oleoresin was
249 performed with a batch size of 20 g of ground black pepper; therefore, the enzyme assisted
250 extraction procedure was repeated with the similar batch size of 20 g black pepper. This was
251 treated with 4 mg α -amylase (in SFE vessel without SPE cartridge) at 60°C and 300 bar for
252 2.25 h with 2 L/min flow rate of CO₂, keeping the ratio of enzyme and black pepper as
253 1:5000. To investigate the effects of flow rate, extraction was also conducted at 1 L/min flow
254 rate of CO₂, with other parameters unchanged.

255 **α -amylase in continuous mode in SC-CO₂ conditions** SC-CO₂ treated fungal α -
256 amylase from *Aspergillus oryzae* in continuous mode has been reported by Senyay-Oncel and
257 Yesil-Celiktas (21), who obtained enhanced activity of the enzyme. In our study, 2 mg and 10
258 mg α -amylase from *Bacillus licheniformis* were treated in separate batches with SC-CO₂ in
259 the SPE cartridge at 60°C and 300 bar under continuous flow of CO₂ at 1 L/min for 2.25 h.

260 **Enzyme assisted SC-CO₂ extraction of black pepper oleoresin in continuous mode**
261 The maximum amount of black pepper that could be charged into a SPE cartridge was 2 g.
262 For continuous extraction, this amount of black pepper could not be subjected to extraction
263 beyond 1 h since the sample matrix was exhausted of its constituents within the first 20 min

264 of extracting time (confirmed by preliminary trials). Therefore, continuous mode of enzyme
265 assisted SC-CO₂ extraction of black pepper oleoresin was attempted using a SFE vessel for
266 extraction time of 2.25 h. 20 g of black pepper with 4 mg α -amylase was charged at 60°C and
267 300 bar for 2.25 h extraction with continuous flow of CO₂ at 1 L/min.

268 **Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR)** Effects of SC-CO₂ on catalytic activity and
269 stability of enzymes depend on many factors, chiefly temperature, pressure, water content,
270 compression/expansion cycles, and depressurization rate (34). SC-CO₂ results in structural
271 and/or conformational changes in active sites of enzyme which in turn affect its activity.
272 These changes have been studied by ¹H NMR analysis of the treated enzyme (21).

273 Untreated and SC-CO₂ treated enzyme samples (of both enhanced and reduced activities
274 obtained by continuous mode of SC-CO₂ treatment) were dissolved in DMSO-d₆ and ¹H
275 NMR spectra (relative to tetramethylsilane, TMS) were recorded at 300 MHz on a Bruker
276 Avance DPX-300 instrument at the Indian Association for Cultivation of Science, Kolkata,
277 West Bengal, India.

278 **Densitometric analyses of black pepper extracts** Densitometric analyses of black
279 pepper extracts were conducted to estimate the total piperine content therein. 20 μ L of test
280 samples were spotted as bands of 8 mm length on pre-coated silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ Al plates (200
281 mm X 100 mm) using Camag Linomat 5 (M/s Camag, Switzerland). Distance between two
282 consecutive bands was kept 10 mm. The chromatogram was developed in the solvent system
283 - toluene: ethyl acetate = 7: 3 at 25 \pm 2°C in a Twin Trough Chamber (200 mm X 100 mm).
284 The plates were scanned with Camag TLC Scanner 3 at 337 nm using a Deuterium lamp at a
285 scanning speed of 20 mm/s. Amount of piperine present in the extracts was determined from
286 the standard curve prepared using pure piperine.

287 **Evaluation of phytochemical properties of black pepper extracts *in vitro*** Antioxidant
288 activity of the extracts was determined by measuring the radical scavenging activity of DPPH

289 (35) and expressed as IC₅₀ values (mg/mL). Total phenolic content was estimated by Folin-
290 Ciocalteu's reagent (36) and expressed as mg gallic acid equivalent/g of dry powder of black
291 pepper. Estimation of reducing power as mg BHT/g of dry black pepper powder was carried
292 out according to the method of Oyaizu (37). Total phenolic content and reducing power of
293 black pepper extracts were estimated from their respective standard curves of gallic acid and
294 BHT. Anti-inflammatory activity of the extracts was determined by nitric oxide (NO)
295 scavenging assay and expressed as IC₅₀ values (mg/mL) (38).

296 **Statistical analyses** All experiments were conducted in triplicate and the data are
297 expressed as means ± SD of three independent experimental runs. Statistical analysis was
298 performed with IBM SPSS Statistics software version 20 (IBM, USA). Duncan's multiple
299 range tests with P-value < 0.05 were used to verify the significance of all tests.

300 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

301 **Characterization of black pepper powder** Proximate analysis of Malabar black pepper
302 powder showed that it contains 5.9 ± 0.1% moisture, 13.6 ± 0.1% protein, 1.5 ± 0.1% fat, 8.9
303 ± 0.1% crude fibre, 5.4 ± 0.1% ash and 58.4 ± 0.1% carbohydrates on a dry weight basis.
304 Starch constituted the major portion of carbohydrates, amounting to 30.4 ± 0.1% of dry black
305 pepper.

306 **Extraction of essential oil and oleoresin from black pepper by conventional methods**

307 Yield of essential oil by hydro-distillation was poor for Malabar black pepper (0.47 ± 0.02 g
308 oil/100 g dry sample). For solvent extraction, yield by the reflux method was highest (9.1 ±
309 0.1 g/100 g dry sample), followed by that obtained by shake flask extraction for 3 h (5.5 ± 0.1
310 g/100 g dry sample), shake flask extraction for 1 h (5.5 ± 0.1 g/100 g dry sample) while the
311 lowest yield was obtained by the Soxhlet method (5.4 ± 0.1 g/100 g dry sample).

312 **SC-CO₂ extraction of black pepper oleoresin** The yields together with the
313 phytochemical properties and total piperine content of SC-CO₂ extracts of black pepper at
314 different temperature-pressure regimes are shown in Table 1. Among all the experimental
315 runs conducted, the highest yield of the extract with best combination of phytochemical
316 properties (antioxidant activity, total phenolic content, reducing power and anti-inflammatory
317 activity) was obtained at 60°C and 300 bar. These optimized T-P conditions were employed
318 for enzymatic SC-CO₂ extraction of black pepper oleoresin, as well as for SC-CO₂ treatment
319 of α -amylase.

320 **α -amylase in batch mode in SC-CO₂ conditions** SC-CO₂ treatment of α -amylase in
321 batch mode at 60°C and 300 bar significantly increased the specific activity of enzyme when
322 the treatment was conducted for 2.25 h (P = 0.000) and 4.25 h (P = 0.000) with 2 mg
323 lyophilized enzyme in each batch. A significant (P = 0.000) decrease in specific activity of
324 the enzyme was observed with increased batch size (2 mg to 10 mg enzyme) (Table 2).
325 Maximum increase of the specific activity of enzyme was obtained at 2.25 h with 2 mg batch
326 size. Under these conditions, the specific activity of the enzyme was found to be 1.25 times
327 higher (329 ± 5 U/mg protein) than that of the untreated enzyme (264 ± 4 U/mg protein).
328 From these sets of runs, time of SC-CO₂ treatment of enzyme was set at 2.25 h and this was
329 also employed as the total extraction time in enzyme-assisted extraction of black pepper
330 oleoresin.

331 **Enzyme assisted SC-CO₂ extraction of black pepper oleoresin in batch mode** With
332 the use of 'SPE cartridge' in enzyme-assisted SC-CO₂ extraction, there was a 88% increase in
333 the yield of black pepper extract compared to the yield of extract without enzymatic treatment
334 (Table 3); whereas, use of 'SFE vessel' for SC-CO₂ extraction showed 36% increase in yield
335 for enzyme-assisted extraction with respect to extraction without enzymatic treatment to the
336 sample. In either experiment (using SPE cartridge and SFE vessel), a CO₂ flow rate of 2

337 L/min was applied during the dynamic time of extraction at 60°C and 300 bar. Although an
338 increased yield of the extract was obtained using SPE cartridge, it was too low for conducting
339 phytochemical assays. Enzyme assisted SC-CO₂ extraction with 1 L/min flow rate of CO₂
340 showed 53% increase in yield of extract at extraction conditions, similar to those employed at
341 2 L/min flow rate of CO₂.

342 **α -amylase in continuous mode in SC-CO₂ conditions** Specific activity of fresh α -
343 amylase was 264 ± 4 U/mg protein, which increased to 561 ± 6 U/mg protein after
344 continuous mode of SC-CO₂ treatment using 2 mg enzyme. Therefore, SC-CO₂ treatment
345 caused 2.13 times increase in specific activity of α -amylase. We obtained a significantly
346 higher ($P = 0.000$) increase in activity of α -amylase, compared to 67.7% increase (i.e., 1.68
347 times increase) in activity of fungal enzyme reported by Senyay-Oncel and Yesil-Celiktas
348 (21). However, when the batch size was increased to 10 mg, SC-CO₂ treatment on α -amylase
349 caused 38.5% decrease in specific activity of the enzyme. To investigate the reason behind
350 this behaviour of the enzyme, ¹H NMR analysis of the treated enzyme was performed. NMR
351 spectrum showed that this decrease in the activity of the enzyme was due to disappearance of
352 hydrogen bonds possibly in the active site of the enzyme (Fig. 2C).

353 According to Zagrobelny and Bright (39), protein conformation changes during
354 pressurization and depressurization steps in a high-pressure batch system. More importantly,
355 loss in enzyme activity may be caused by the depressurization step at the collection end (40).
356 Since there was no depressurization step in the continuous mode, we opine that this resulted
357 in 2.13 times increase of specific activity of α -amylase compared to 1.25 times increase of the
358 same in the batch mode.

359 **Enzyme assisted SC-CO₂ extraction of black pepper oleoresin in continuous mode**
360 In continuous mode, the yield obtained by non-enzymatic SC-CO₂ extraction of black pepper
361 oleoresin at 60°C and 300 bar for 2.25 h was 4.6 ± 0.4 g extract/100 g dry black pepper,

362 whereas yield of the same in batch mode under similar conditions was 2.1 ± 0.3 g extract/100
363 g dry black pepper. Our results indicate that continuous mode of SC-CO₂ extraction increased
364 the yield of extract by 121.2% without enzymatic treatment of black pepper. However, in
365 case of enzyme assisted SC-CO₂ extraction in continuous mode, enzymatic hydrolysis of
366 black pepper enhanced the yield of extract by 15% (5.3 ± 0.4 g extract/100 g dry black
367 pepper) (Table 3), which was significantly ($P = 0.000$) lower than the increase of yield of
368 extract (53%) in batch mode under similar conditions of extraction. These findings attest to
369 the fact that an incubation time is required by the enzyme for hydrolysis of the starch present
370 in the black pepper matrix which was attained in the batch mode resulting in enhanced yield
371 of oleoresin from the pepper matrix.

372 For experiments of SC-CO₂ treatment on α -amylase at 60°C and 300 bar, both batch and
373 continuous modes of treatment enhanced the specific activity of the enzyme. In batch mode,
374 the increase was 1.25 times; whereas, in continuous mode the specific activity increased by
375 2.13 times. For enzyme-assisted extraction of black pepper oleoresin, under similar SC-CO₂
376 conditions, batch mode of extraction with 2 L/min flow rate of CO₂ enhanced the yield of
377 extract by 36% however 1 L/min flow rate of CO₂ increased the yield by 53%. For
378 continuous mode of enzyme-assisted extraction of black pepper oleoresin, 15% enhanced
379 yield of extract was obtained with 1 L/min flow rate of CO₂ at 60°C and 300 bar.

380 **Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectra of enzyme samples** The NMR spectrum
381 of α -amylase with enhanced activity (Fig. 2B) showed changes in pattern of peaks at
382 positions 0.81 ppm and 0.98 ppm, respectively, compared to the spectrum of the untreated
383 enzyme (Fig. 2A). The singlet peak at position 0.81 ppm modified to a doublet peak and the
384 doublet peak at position 0.98 ppm modified to a triplet peak in the spectrum of SC-CO₂
385 treated enzyme. Further, the ratios of intensities of peaks at positions 0.81 ppm and 0.98 ppm
386 and those at 4.22 ppm and 4.41 ppm were significantly modified. Also, a new peak was

387 observed in the NMR spectrum of SC-CO₂ treated enzyme at position 3.00 ppm. Chemical
388 shifts observed in untreated and that in treated enzyme samples were: 0.81 to 0.83 ppm, 4.41
389 to 4.40 ppm, 7.20 to 7.19 ppm and 7.52 to 7.50 ppm. These changes in the NMR spectra
390 suggested that SC-CO₂ altered the conformational arrangement and/or structural framework
391 of α -amylase, possibly at its active site, which resulted in significant ($P = 0.000$) enhanced
392 activity (2.13 times) of the treated enzyme.

393 On the other hand, only one peak was observed in the NMR spectrum of SC-CO₂ treated α -
394 amylase with reduced activity at position 1.24 ppm (Fig. 2C). This indicates that with higher
395 batch size, SC-CO₂ significantly altered the arrangement of bonds in the enzyme which
396 caused reduction in its activity. However, since the enzyme still retained specific activity of
397 68 ± 4 U/mg protein (compared to 264 ± 4 U/mg protein of the fresh enzyme), it can be
398 concluded that the enzyme was not denatured by the SC-CO₂ treatment.

399 **Densitometric analysis of black pepper extracts** Total piperine content of each extract
400 was estimated by HPTLC (High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography) at 337 nm using
401 standard piperine ($R_f = 0.3$) as reference. Maximum increase (10.6% at 2 L/min CO₂ flow and
402 11.2% at 1 L/min CO₂ flow at 60°C and 300 bar) of total piperine content of black pepper
403 extracts was observed when enzyme-assisted extraction was carried out in SFE vessel in
404 batch mode (Table 4).

405 **Evaluation of phytochemical properties of black pepper extracts** The antioxidant
406 potency of the extracts was presented by IC₅₀ values which denote the concentration of the
407 sample required to decrease the DPPH free radicals by 50%. Lower IC₅₀ value signifies
408 higher antioxidant potency. From Table 4, it is evident that among the SC-CO₂ extracts, the
409 highest increase in antioxidant activity (i.e., maximum decrease in IC₅₀ value of DPPH
410 radical scavenging activity) was from 3.3 ± 0.1 to 2.7 ± 0.1 mg/mL for extract obtained with
411 enzymatic extraction of black pepper oleoresin in batch mode at 60°C and 300 bar with 1

412 L/min CO₂ flow. One of the most important classes of secondary metabolites of plants is the
413 phenolic compounds. Total phenolic content in the black pepper extracts were measured
414 using Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent and was expressed in terms of gallic acid equivalent.
415 Reducing power of extracts is associated with its antioxidant activity. Compounds with
416 reducing power indicate that they are electron donors and can reduce the oxidized
417 intermediates of lipid peroxidation processes, so that they can act as primary and secondary
418 antioxidants. For the above mentioned extraction conditions, the increase in total phenolic
419 content was from 0.13 ± 0.01 to 0.18 ± 0.01 mg GAE/g of dry black pepper and increase in
420 reducing power was from 1.9 ± 0.1 to 2.2 ± 0.1 mg BHT/g of dry black pepper. These
421 observations affirm that enzyme-assisted extraction of black pepper oleoresin in batch mode
422 of operation (at a flow rate of 1 L/min of CO₂) is preferable for SC-CO₂ extraction, for
423 enhanced phytochemical potencies of its extracts. Anti-inflammatory activity was measured
424 *in vitro* by IC₅₀ value of NO radical scavenging activity of extracts. The increase in anti-
425 inflammatory activity was maximum (from 1.74 ± 0.02 to 1.63 ± 0.03 mg/mL) in the extract
426 obtained with enzymatic treatment of black pepper in batch mode at 60°C and 300 bar with 2
427 L/min CO₂ flow. Overall, we may conclude that application of α -amylase to black pepper
428 matrix for SC-CO₂ extraction played a significant role in improving phytochemical properties
429 of its extracts.

430 In conclusion, this study demonstrated that α -amylase assisted SC-CO₂ extraction of black
431 pepper oleoresin enhanced the yield of piperine-rich extract with good combination of
432 phytochemical properties (antioxidant activity, total phenolic content, reducing power, and
433 anti-inflammatory activity). Optimization of the process parameters was conducted and the
434 optimized conditions that provided the maximum yield of piperine (1.3 ± 0.1 mg/g of dry
435 black pepper) and the best combination of phytochemical properties among other extracts
436 investigated here, were a sample size of 20 g of black pepper powder of particle diameter 0.4

437 ± 0.02 mm at 60°C and 300 bar at a flow rate of 2 L/min of CO₂. SC-CO₂ treatment of α -
438 amylase and enzyme-assisted extraction of black pepper oleoresin were conducted at the
439 optimized extraction conditions in batch and continuous modes. SC-CO₂ treated α -amylase
440 showed enhanced specific activity in either mode: 1.25 times in the batch mode and 2.13
441 times in the continuous mode. ¹H NMR analysis revealed that the enhancement of specific
442 activity was due to an alteration in the conformational arrangement of α -amylase, possibly at
443 its active site. Enzyme-assisted SC-CO₂ extraction in the batch mode increased the yield of
444 black pepper extract by 53%, while only 15% increase in yield was obtained in the
445 continuous mode of extraction. We opine that the equilibration time (static time) of the batch
446 mode possibly served as the incubation time for the enzymatic reaction leading to enhanced
447 yield of extract and piperine content therein. The enzyme however had no incubation time in
448 the continuous mode of extraction. This extract could have promising applications as food
449 and therapeutic supplements.

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578 **FIGURE**

579 FIG. 1. Schematic diagram of SPE cartridge loaded with α -amylase.

586 FIG. 2. ¹H NMR Spectra of α-amylase. A) Untreated enzyme, B) Treated enzyme with
587 highest activity, C) Treated enzyme with lowest activity.

589

TABLE 1. Yield and phytochemical properties of black pepper extracts in full factorial

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design.

Pressure (bar)	Temperature (°C)	Yield of extract (g extract/100 g dry black pepper) ^a	Piperine content (mg/g of dry black pepper) ^a	Antioxidant activity (IC ₅₀ of DPPH radical scavenging activity) (mg/ml) ^a	Total phenolic content (mg GAE/g of dry Black pepper) ^a	Reducing power content (mg BHT/g of dry Black pepper) ^a	Anti-inflammatory activity (IC ₅₀ of NO radical scavenging activity) (mg/ml) ^a
200	40	2.72 ± 0.14 ^b	1.13 ± 0.07 ^b	4.14 ± 0.17 ^b	0.11 ± 0.05 ^b	2.80 ± 0.12 ^b	3.74 ± 0.09 ^b
200	50	2.37 ± 0.10 ^c	1.02 ± 0.09 ^c	4.19 ± 0.15 ^c	0.09 ± 0.02 ^c	1.76 ± 0.18 ^c	4.19 ± 0.11 ^c
200	60	2.32 ± 0.15 ^d	0.94 ± 0.06 ^d	4.32 ± 0.18 ^d	0.08 ± 0.07 ^c	1.42 ± 0.16 ^d	4.92 ± 0.07 ^d
300	40	3.36 ± 0.16 ^e	1.16 ± 0.11 ^e	3.97 ± 0.16 ^e	0.09 ± 0.06 ^c	2.39 ± 0.18 ^e	3.76 ± 0.10 ^b
300	50	3.65 ± 0.15 ^f	1.17 ± 0.08 ^e	3.23 ± 0.15 ^f	0.12 ± 0.03 ^b	2.64 ± 0.14 ^f	3.54 ± 0.14 ^e
300	60	3.87 ± 0.16 ^g	1.31 ± 0.06 ^f	2.79 ± 0.17 ^g	0.14 ± 0.05 ^d	3.05 ± 0.16 ^g	3.11 ± 0.12 ^f
500	40	2.77 ± 0.13 ^h	1.19 ± 0.10 ^e	2.96 ± 0.14 ^h	0.07 ± 0.03 ^c	2.73 ± 0.13 ^h	3.75 ± 0.09 ^b
500	50	3.74 ± 0.15 ⁱ	1.31 ± 0.07 ^f	2.93 ± 0.16 ^h	0.09 ± 0.04 ^c	2.89 ± 0.11 ⁱ	3.57 ± 0.08 ^e
500	60	3.79 ± 0.14 ⁱ	1.28 ± 0.08 ^f	2.91 ± 0.15 ^h	0.08 ± 0.02 ^c	2.95 ± 0.18 ^j	3.48 ± 0.12 ^g

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^a Yield of extraction, piperine content, antioxidant activity, total phenolic content, reducing power and anti-inflammatory activity are mean ± SD of three independent SFE runs of three batches of black pepper.

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Different letters in a column indicate significant differences at P < 0.05.

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TABLE 2. SC-CO₂ treatment of α -amylase at 60°C, 300 bar in batch mode.

Sample	Amount of Enzyme (mg)	Time of Treatment (h)	Specific Activity (U/mg protein) ^a
Untreated enzyme	na	na	263.56 ± 4.35 ^b
Treated enzyme	2	2.25	329.42 ± 4.67 ^c
Treated enzyme	2	4.25	302.07 ± 2.98 ^d
Treated enzyme	5	2.25	186.42 ± 3.19 ^e
Treated enzyme	5	4.25	200.40 ± 5.52 ^f
Treated enzyme	10	2.25	100.30 ± 3.90 ^g
Treated enzyme	10	4.25	128.09 ± 4.00 ^h

596 ^a Specific activities of enzyme are mean ± SD of three independent runs of enzyme in SC-CO₂
597 condition.

598 na- not applicable.

599 Different letters in a column indicate significant differences at P < 0.05.

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TABLE 3. Enzyme assisted SC-CO₂ extraction of black pepper at 60°C, 300 bar.

Sample Holder	Extraction Mode	Sample Charged for Extraction	Flow Rate of CO ₂ (L/min)	Yield of Extract (g extract/100 g dry black pepper) ^a	Increase in Yield of Extraction (%)
SPE cartridge	Batch ^{aa}	2 g sample without enzyme	2	0.65 ± 0.05 ^b	
		2 g sample with 0.4 mg enzyme	2	1.22 ± 0.01 ^c	87.69
Extraction vessel (SS 316)	Batch ^{aa}	20 g sample without enzyme	2	2.82 ± 0.22 ^d	
		20 g sample with 4 mg enzyme	2	3.83 ± 0.18 ^e	35.82
	Continuous ^{bb}	20 g sample without enzyme	1	2.08 ± 0.20 ^f	
		20 g sample with 4 mg enzyme	1	3.19 ± 0.18 ^g	53.36
		20 g sample without enzyme	1	4.60 ± 0.16 ^h	
		20 g sample with 4 mg enzyme	1	5.27 ± 0.17 ⁱ	14.56

613 ^a Yield of extraction are mean ± SD of three independent SFE runs of three batches of black
614 pepper.

615 ^{aa} Total extraction time consists of 2 h static and 15 min dynamic time.

616 ^{bb} Total extraction time consists of 2 h 15 min dynamic time.

617 Different letters in a column in each category indicate significant differences at P < 0.05.

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TABLE 4. Phytochemical properties of SC-CO₂ extracts of black pepper.

Sample	Yield of piperine (mg/g dry black pepper) ^a	Antioxidant activity (IC ₅₀ of DPPH radical scavenging activity) (mg/ml) ^a	Total phenolic content (mg GAE/g of dry black pepper) ^a	Reducing power content (mg BHT/g of dry black pepper) ^a	Anti-inflammatory activity (IC ₅₀ of NO radical scavenging activity) (mg/ml) ^a
Batch mode, 2 L/min, without enzyme	1.23 ± 0.05 ^d	3.00 ± 0.15 ^f	0.11 ± 0.01 ^g	1.90 ± 0.10 ^g	1.74 ± 0.02 ^d
Batch mode, 2 L/min, with enzyme	1.36 ± 0.04 ^e	2.60 ± 0.14 ^g	0.15 ± 0.02 ^h	2.30 ± 0.11 ^h	1.63 ± 0.03 ^e
Batch mode, 1 L/min, without enzyme	0.93 ± 0.02 ^f	3.27 ± 0.11 ^h	0.13 ± 0.01 ^g	1.89 ± 0.12 ^g	2.24 ± 0.04 ^f
Batch mode, 1 L/min, with enzyme	1.03 ± 0.03 ^g	2.74 ± 0.12 ⁱ	0.18 ± 0.01 ^g	2.17 ± 0.13 ⁱ	2.15 ± 0.02 ^g
Continuous mode, without enzyme	1.36 ± 0.02 ^h	2.51 ± 0.11 ^j	0.14 ± 0.02 ^g	2.71 ± 0.14 ^j	2.84 ± 0.01 ^h
Continuous mode, with enzyme	1.45 ± 0.04 ⁱ	2.01 ± 0.13 ^k	0.17 ± 0.02 ^h	3.04 ± 0.12 ^k	2.74 ± 0.03 ⁱ

628 ^a Yield of piperine, IC₅₀ value of DPPH radical scavenging activity, total phenolic content,
629 reducing power content, and NO radical scavenging activity of extracts are mean ± SD of
630 three independent extraction runs of three batches of black pepper.
631 Different letters in a column indicate significant differences at P < 0.05.
632